

Non-Contact Safety for Stationary Robots Through Optical Entry Detection With a Co-Moving 3D-Camera

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Abstract—Safety is a central challenge in human-robot collaboration. Particularly in higher collaboration levels, separating safety devices, such as fences, are no longer needed and must be replaced by intelligent sensor-based systems. Of particular interest is the adaptive speed control of the robot. This work presents a methodology to adaptively control the end-effector velocity of the robot based on the distances to dynamic environmental objects. The method combines distance measurement and environmental subtraction with conservative velocity estimation using robot-specific stopping distances and is available in real-time. Data acquisition is performed using a co-moving 3D camera sensor attached to the robot structure.

Index Terms—safety, entry detection, human-robot collaboration, industrial manipulators

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a method for detecting dynamic objects within a robot’s workspace and control its velocity accordingly. In practice, occlusion from workshop items and the robot itself prevents the usage of only static sensing systems for safety measures. Therefore, a combination of global static sensors and local co-moving sensors on the robot structure (here: third arm link) guarantees robust safety in presence of occlusion. We propose a method combining voxel-based background modeling and a polynomial velocity approximation according to ISO 13855 [1] and ISO 10218-2 [2]. With the proposed pipeline, real-time computation is possible using an embedded PC, which is a major factor in robot safety as computing time directly correlates with the stopping distance of the robot.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- Developed lenient detection pipeline for dynamic objects entering the robot’s workspace using co-moving sensors
- Proposed novel approximation method for stopping distance and robot velocity using the applicable standards

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II. RELATED WORK

Human-robot collaboration (HRC) is a relatively young field in industrial assembly. Typically, humans and robots share a spatial and partly temporal workspace in HRC processes. Bdiwi, Pfeiffer, and Sterzing [3] define four interaction levels including a collaborative zone shared by humans and robots. In this zone, the robot travels at reduced speed. Optical safety systems available on the market typically define static zones in which a fixed speed limit is set (e.g., PILZ SafetyEYE [4]). Hence, such safety measures are unsuitable for the collaborative zone.

Current dynamic methods rely on stationary 3D cameras. Leso, Zilkova, and Vacek [5] lay out a safety system that detects the disruption of an optical barrier. The geometry of the barrier is adapted to the acute robot configuration and projected optically onto the work surface. Vogel, Walter, and Elkmann [6] describe a similar approach using frequency-modulated light. These approaches also do not allow use in a collaborative zone, as they also only lead to an emergency stop - albeit less restrictive than the market-available systems.

Kuhn, Gecks, and Henrich [7] use image differencing to detect people entering with one or more cameras. Fabricio and de Luca [8] describe an approach to bind the depth values of multiple 3D cameras to a global fixed grid. They then compute in real-time the distance from the human to a fixed number of target points on the robot structure. Saveriano and Lee [9] detect field entry via a stationary camera using *OpenNI* and filter it via a Kalman filter (constant velocity model). Subsequently, evasion trajectories are determined via a modulation approach. However, while these methods are suitable for the collaborative zone, they use only stationary sensors and are thus susceptible to occlusions in the environment.

Our approach compensates for these occluded areas by using a co-moving sensor system. This safety system can be used independently or in combination with fixed cameras, hence complementing the existing systems. Song and

Fig. 1. Setup in the IGMR laboratory: 3D camera (Orbbec Astra Pro) mounted on Universal Robots UR10e robotic arm

Huang [10] describe a similar approach for mobile robots based on optical flow. However, this only detects static objects in the environment and is thus not applicable to the described scenario with dynamic environmental objects. Copot [11] describes a generalist scheme for velocity control with a co-moving camera based on feature extraction. However, the control scheme has not yet been implemented and validated in a real application.

III. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION, CONTEXT AND INTERFACES

The safety system to be proposed in the following consists of a 3D camera mounted on the third link of a serial robot structure (see Figure 1). The camera can be oriented either facing towards the end effector (EE) or to the side. The combination of several cameras is possible. Access to the robot controller is decoupled, making the overall system scalable in the number of components.

For this paper, a Universal Robots UR10e and an Orbbec Astra Pro Time-of-Flight (ToF) camera are used. Both systems are connected to an Nvidia Jetson TX-2 embedded PC, which runs the safety application. Trajectory planning and control is performed by a separate computer. All subsystems are integrated and connected using the Robot Operating System (ROS).

The task of the safety system is to monitor the workspace and control the EE speed based on the distance of the robot to entering objects. The latter may be people, mobile workshop furniture, or other robots. Safety systems are subject to high real-time requirements, because large cycle times ultimately lead to more restrictive behavior of the robot. Due to this, some operations cannot be performed that would require an exact computation of the speed based on the corresponding standards ISO 13855 [1] (safety of machinery) and ISO 10218-2 [2] (safety of industrial robots). To reduce cycle time, following steps are applied:

- (1) No classification of the entering objects
- (2) Thereby, no segmentation of body parts
- (3) Purely linear motion prediction of objects
- (4) No inclusion of all robot joints or the exact contour of the body in the distance computation

In particular, the lack of segmentation (2) means that the worst possible contact must be assumed at all times. According to ISO/TS 15066 [12], this is the contact with the head. ISO/TS 15066 specifies safety requirements for collaborative robot systems and the working environment.

Fig. 2. Discretized background model of the IGMR laboratory with a voxel resolution of 0.1 m.

Since in ROS the setting of the EE speed is only possible at the support points of the robot trajectory (using *MoveIt*¹), which cannot be discretized according to the need of the safety application, the speed is set directly in the robot driver via a serial interface. This is done via the software development kit (SDK) of the manufacturer Universal Robots².

IV. ENVIRONMENT MODELING AND ENTRY DETECTION

The robot's environment is discretized using an octree [13]. An octree is a data structure in which cubes are divided hierarchically into smaller cubes of same size; called voxels. Variable discretization levels depending on the point density allow low access times to the data structure. For the safety methodology, however, the tree structure is only used to accelerate searching. The object hierarchy within the tree is created before the actual modeling process with a fixed resolution (voxel width) and thus moved to an offline step. The voxels only carry their occupancy state as binary information, i.e. *occupied* or *free*. In the modeling process, point clouds from different robot configurations are inserted into the environment model. This can be done (partially) autonomously. The procedure is analogous to our already validated method for discretizing large workspaces, which can be found in [14].

The background model is created at a height between 0.3 and 2.5 m from the ground. The values correspond to ISO 10218-2 [2]. The partial background model of the IGMR laboratory is shown in Figure 2.

A. Entry Detection

For the detection of entries into the monitored area, the incoming point clouds are compared with the generated discretized background model. The structure of the octree reduces access times to the backend. If there is an occupied voxel at the location of a point in the point cloud, this point is filtered. Since this only depends on the size of the point cloud itself, the complexity of the comparison does not scale with the size of the background model, but linearly with the size of the point cloud. Thus, the background model may be configured to be discretized arbitrarily wide and/or fine.

Once the entry into the monitored area is detected, the shortest distance d_{tar} to the robot must be computed. For this purpose, two critical points are identified: The robot structure

¹<https://moveit.ros.org/>

²https://github.com/UniversalRobots/Universal_Robots_ROS_Driver

Fig. 3. Sketch of the robot structure and critical distances normal to the spanned plane ($d_{tar,1}$) and to the EE ($d_{tar,2}$).

(blow, crush) and the EE itself (stab, crush). The distance to the robot structure $d_{tar,1}$ is computed as the point-to-line distance from entry point to structure. A plane is spanned by joint 1 and joint 4 and shifted by the largest geometrical casing width of the enclosed links. We define the base joint as 0. Plane and entry detection are then projected onto the ground, hence reducing the distance computation to a planar problem (line and point entity). The distance to the EE $d_{tar,2}$ is computed using the Euclidean point-to-point distance to the point of attack of the end effector. The shorter distance is then selected and passed to the safety system: $d_{tar} = \min(d_{tar,1}, d_{tar,2})$. The distances are schematically sketched in Figure 3.

B. Compensation of Uncertain Sensor Data

Challenges arise when 3D cameras with unreliable depth values (e.g. stereo-vision) are used. Three filters are implemented to deal with moderately disturbed data:

- 1) Nearest-Neighbors
- 2) Flicker Limiter
- 3) Moving Average

Nearest-Neighbors (NN) [15] is used to filter out small field entries. Since the detection of a human or other dynamic objects always includes several hundred points, clusters of disturbances can be detected in a targeted manner. NN computes the Euclidean distance to the nearest neighbor points and filters out those with a defined maximum distance over less than k neighbors (here $k = 1000$). This procedure is problematic if many field entries are to be expected in the boundary region, where the human is partly outside the area covered by the background model, and may therefore not generate clusters of sufficient size. This leads to false negatives (FN). The filter is applied after entry detection.

The **Flicker Limiter** is used to filter out strongly fluctuating entry detections. If the Euclidean distance between two entry detections exceeds a threshold for n consecutive frames (here: $n = 5$), the next detections are filtered until the detection is stable for the same amount of frames. According to our observations, the entry point jumps strongly when the depth values are unreliable and no real entry exists. The limiter thus filters false positive (FP) detections.

The depth values are usually stable at field entry. To be able to filter out small fluctuations here as well, a **Moving Average** with a small horizon (≤ 5 time steps) is used. This leads to a smoothing of the distance values, which makes them less accurate, but easier to process for connected

systems. Flicker Limiter and Moving Average are applied after the shortest distance computation.

Since all filters - especially NN - have an influence on the computing time, it is recommended to use a camera with stable depth values (e.g. TOF camera) and to switch off those filters that are not needed in the respective application.

C. Modeling the End-Effector and Tools

The model described so far only allows to detect entries when there is no occlusion by the end effector itself or a mounted tool. To cover this efficiently, another octree with a high degree of discretization (1-10 mm) is provided at the tool flange. The tool is modeled as a cylinder and is fixed at the EE coordinate frame. As the model moves relative to the robot configuration, point clouds are applied on the tool model by solving forward kinematics. Forward kinematics are available in real-time. Thus, the tool can be effectively filtered out and is subject to the same time constraints as the general background model. In the case of a mounted tool, the EE point for the distance computation (compare Figure 3) is moved to the front side of the tool. This is usually the location of the point of attack towards the environment.

V. CONSERVATIVE SPEED ESTIMATION

As input to the safety computation, the current joint configuration \mathbf{q} and absolute EE velocity v_{rob} , as well as the distance to the entering object d_{tar} are used. In addition, data on kinematics and stopping behavior are needed. According to ISO 10218-2 [2] reference values for the determination of the stopping behavior must be defined by the manufacturer. These can be found in the respective manual (e.g. of the UR10e [16], compare Figure 4). The standardized overtravel distances and times are dependent on

- extension I (percentage of distance between base and EE over maximum range),
- velocity or so-called *Program Overwrite POV* (percentage of maximum velocity of reference joint, or EE), and
- payload m (percentage of maximum payload).

Consequently, there are nine reference curves for stopping time and distance for each joint (see Figure 4). The pure linear interpolation of these curves over all input values (interpolation over three levels) leads to an unacceptably high computing time. Additionally, it only provides information about the stopping behavior of the robot and not of the overall system, including the human and the interfaces. In order to enable a comprehensive and fast computation of the allowed speed in the vicinity of humans, a more elaborate methodology is required that includes more subsystems (human, robot, etc.), but at the same time realizes a sufficiently fast computing time.

A. Definition of the System Times

The computation of the EE speed is a predictive-iterative procedure. First, cycle times and dead times of the system must be recorded. Dead times t_{dead} arise from the data frequency of the sensor $f_{sen} = 1/t_{sen}$, the maximum computing time of the safety algorithm t_{alg} and the real data rate of the physical interfaces t_{int} (connector and cable):

$$t_{dead} = \frac{1}{f_{sen}} + t_{int} + t_{alg} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Overtravel (in m) of the UR10e base joint for 33% payload [16]

The dead time of the sensor and the interfaces can be taken from the data sheets or be computed (e.g. from the transfer rate). In our case, the used USB3.0 cable has a real transfer rate of 450 MB/s and thus induces a delay of $t_{int} \approx 21.8$ ms for the camera sensor (640x480 px, 30 FPS). The computing time of the algorithm is conservatively estimated and monitored during execution. If a higher computing time occurs, the parameter t_{alg} is increased accordingly.

B. Computation of the Conservative Braking Distance

To simplify the velocity computation, it is assumed that human and robot move linearly towards each other in a direct path at all times. According to ISO 13855 [1], a human moves with a velocity of $v_{hum} = 2$ m/s if a minimum distance (to the robot) of $d_{min} < 0.5$ m is maintained (here: $d_{min} = 0.1$ m). The minimum distance must not be smaller than the detection error. The presented background model has an error in size of voxels (here: $d_{voxel} = 0.1$ m).

To ensure that no contact occurs during operation, the stopping distance must not exceed the accumulated movements during deceleration and the dead time movement, i.e.

$$d_{STOP1} \geq d_{tar} - d_{min} - d_{dead}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$d_{dead} = t_{dead}(v_{hum} + v_{rob}). \quad (3)$$

To achieve a safety-related monitored standstill of the robot, two variants are defined: STOP0 and STOP1. In STOP0, the robot brakes actively via a braking system, while in STOP1 it only decelerates to a stop (with motor braking). For STOP0, the values are given directly and STOP1 is to be determined via the overtravel diagrams (see Figure 4). As already explained in detail, an interpolation of the overtravel in a time-critical system is not purposeful. Moreover, a real system behaves continuously and has no jumps at the support points. Therefore, the interpolation points are first extended by velocity and time dependent terms:

$$\hat{d}_{STOP1} = v_{hum}t_{0,STOP1} + 2I \cdot d_{I,max} \sin\left(\frac{\varphi_{0,STOP1}}{2}\right) \quad (4a)$$

$$\hat{d}_{STOP1} = v_{hum}t_{0,STOP1} + d_{0,STOP1} \quad (4b)$$

with

$$t_{i,STOP1} := t_{i,STOP1}(m, I, POV), \quad (5a)$$

$$\varphi_{i,STOP1} := \varphi_{i,STOP1}(m, I, POV), \quad (5b)$$

$$d_{i,STOP1} := d_{i,STOP1}(m, I, POV). \quad (5c)$$

Fig. 5. Total stopping distance \hat{d}_{STOP1} over robot velocity POV for UR10e at maximum extension

Here, Equation 4 defines the stopping distance by combining overtravel angle (4a) or overtravel (4b) of the corresponding joint (0: base joint) with the overtravel time $t_{i,STOP1}$ incorporating human movement. Manufacturers specify one of the displacement parameters $d_{i,STOP1}$ (overtravel) or $\varphi_{i,STOP1}$ (overtravel angle) in their manuals. Since it is assumed that collision can only occur when the robot is rotating towards the human, considering the base joint is sufficient for a conservative estimation. This virtually reduces the robot to a rotational joint with a rod the length of the current extension, projected onto the base plane. Since Equation 4 combines overtravel time and distance, there are only 27 support points to consider for the base joint instead of the initial 54. To save the interpolation of these support points and to get closer to the real trajectories, these points are approximated by a cubic polynomial. This results in the trajectories in Figure 5. The 27 support points thus become nine continuous functions depending on the velocity for the combinations of payload and extension.

C. Safety Algorithm

For the algorithm, the conservative braking distance and the available distance to the entry object are first compared. If the stopping distance exceeds the minimal distance to the entry point, the speed must be adjusted. This is done by inverting the braking functions. To solve the inverse problem, either a method for general cubic polynomials [17] or an eigenvalue decomposition can be used. Experiments have shown that the general approach may become unstable in certain situations. Therefore, the eigenvalue decomposition $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{Q}^{-1}$ with

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{b}{a} & -\frac{c}{a} & \frac{d_{tar}}{a} \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

is used, where a , b and c are the coefficients of the cubic polynomial $a(POV)^3 + b(POV)^2 + c(POV)$ and the eigenvalue decomposition solves the characteristic polynomial:

$$a(POV)^3 + b(POV)^2 + c(POV) - d_{tar} = 0, \quad (7)$$

with $POV = v_{rob}/v_{rob,max}$.

After the target velocity v_{rob} is determined, the distance covered during deceleration to the target velocity is computed. This is done using a linear acceleration ramp with a predefined acceleration value (in $\%/sec$; see Equation 9).

Algorithm 1 Safety algorithm

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1:  $d_{tar} \leftarrow$  closest point to EE OR plane
2:  $d_{STOP1} \leftarrow$  lookupStop1Distance( $v_{rob}, \mathbf{q}, m$ )
3:  $d_{delta} = d_{tar} - d_{min} - d_{dead}$ 
4: if  $d_{delta} > d_{STOP1}$  then
5:   No adjustment
6: end if
7:  $v_{tar} \leftarrow$  lookupSafeVelocity( $d_{delta}$ )
8:  $d_{ac} \leftarrow$  computeDecelerationDistance( $v_{rob}, v_{tar}$ )
9: if  $d_{delta} < d_{ac}$  then
10:  Emergency brake (STOP0)
11: end if
12: while  $d_{delta} - d_{ac} > 1 \times 10^{-6}$  do
13:   $v_{tar} \leftarrow$  lookupSafeVelocity( $d_{delta} - d_{ac}$ )
14:   $d_{ac} \leftarrow$  computeDecelerationDistance( $v_{rob}, v_{tar}$ )
15: end while
16: send  $v_{tar}$  to robot control
  
```

If a collision occurs again with the accumulated distance, the target velocity is reduced in an iterative procedure, taking into account the acceleration behavior. The path length covered during deceleration or acceleration d_{ac} is computed by

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_{ac} &= t_{dec} v_{hum} + \int_{x=POV_{tar}}^{POV} t_{dec} v_{rob}(x) dx \\
 &= t_{dec} v_{hum} + \frac{v_{rob,max}}{2a_{ac}} (\Delta POV)^3,
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

with

$$v_{rob}(POV) = POV v_{rob,max}, \tag{9a}$$

$$t_{dec} := t_{dec}(\Delta POV) = \frac{\Delta POV}{a_{ac}}, \tag{9b}$$

where a_{ac} is the acceleration ramp over the relative velocity difference $\Delta POV = POV - POV_{tar}$ and POV_{tar} is the relative target velocity. The whole safety method is described in Algorithm 1.

VI. VALIDATION

For validation, the safety system is integrated into the setup described in Section III. The camera points forwards and is angled slightly downward to realize maximum coverage over the EE. A trajectory is implemented via the ROS motion planning framework *MoveIt* that describes a stabbing horizontal motion from minimum to maximum extension. The robot travels at maximum speed with no payload attached and no tool mounted. During the tests, a human enters the workspace at variable speed and different entry angles and positions. In none of the tests could the system be forced to make a mistake. Even in the worst case (entry from the back of the robot), when the human enters the area covered by the camera, the robot stops or reduces its speed in time, preventing contact. An exemplary speed trajectory with and without entry is shown in Figure 6. The described demonstration scenario is further depicted in a project video³.

Fig. 6. EE velocity profile of the UR10e with stabbing motion without detection (blue) and when a human enters the monitored space head-on (red). The person enters the workspace at approximately 12 sec. The velocity is lowered adaptively relative to the original velocity profile.

Fig. 7. Cycle times of the safety algorithm with and without (IDLE) entry into the protected area at low and high noise level; mean values annotated.

In addition to functionality, the computing time is of particular interest. The higher the computing time, the higher the dead time and lower the allowed speed in the vicinity of a human. For the validation, two cases are distinguished according to the level of sensor noise. For low noise level, the system is operated in regular mode. For high levels of noise, defects are selectively added to the background model, inducing about 36,000 noisy data points in the detections during operation. Thus, the point cloud for nearest neighbor computation and entry detection is much larger in the latter case. The tests for computing time are done with a static target in the workspace and the same trajectory as in the initially described test scenario. The results are shown in Figure 7. With pure monitoring without entry of a dynamic object, the safety system achieves an average cycle time of 10.44 ms (27.73 ms at high noise level). When entering the protected area, the system requires an average of 35.14 ms (89.19 ms) until the speed is set on the robot. These values are the pure computing time from data input to safety system output. When the noise level is low, the system is available in hard real-time (each frame can be evaluated). In operation, the dead time of the hardware (here a maximum of 55.13 ms) must be considered for the real delay. This is taken into account in the safety computation (see Section V-A).

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xJROaSusnQE>

VII. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This paper describes the design and methodology of a safety system for serial robots using a co-moving 3D camera. The methodology consists of building a background model using an octree and then filtering the input point cloud for entering objects. Then, based on the distance of the detection to the robot and other metrics, the optimal interaction speed is conservatively estimated and set accordingly on the robot. The methodology includes various dead times and compensates for uncertainties in the input signal via appropriate filtering. Finally, the overall safety system is validated based on functionality and computing time, showing its real-time potential on embedded hardware.

The described methodology is more conservative than necessary. This is because only the base joint is considered for the computation. If all joint motions are used, there is no need to further assume that the robot always moves towards the human. This would allow the implementation of collision avoidance, which approaches alternative trajectory points while aiming to maintain a constant speed. Furthermore, ROS is not suitable for a safety-critical system, since the framework does not ensure that interface communication is performed and messages are sent or received correctly. Options here would be to implement the safety system on an industrial PC or in ROS2, which is set up to guarantee communication and real-time capability in the future.

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